

A Cross Sectional Study of Awareness Regarding Smoking and Its Adverse Health Effects among the Visitors of Tertiary Care Hospital, Western Part of Gujarat

Bharti Koria¹, Sachin Bhimani², Khusbu Patel³, Kinjal Waghela⁴, Kiran Chaudhary⁵, Hiral Raval⁶

¹Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, PDU Medical College, Rajkot, Gujarat

²Senior Resident, Department of Neurosurgery, PDU Medical College, Rajkot, Gujarat

^{3,4,5}Interns, Government Medical College, Bhavnagar, Gujarat

⁶Public Health Expert, Government of Gujarat, Gujarat

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Bharti Koria, ¹Associate Professor, Community Medicine Department, PDU Medical College, Rajkot, Gujarat, drbhartikoria@gmail.com

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Smoking contributes to millions of deaths and continues to do so on. This study was done with purpose of assessing the knowledge and practices among smokers visiting to tertiary care hospital

Methodology: This was a cross sectional study done in in a tertiary care hospital, Gujarat from Aug-Nov 2021. Data were collected by preformed pretested Performa by taking informed consent from participants. Data entered and analyzed in Microsoft excel.

Results: In this study, 91% participants were male, 54% between 36-50 years of age and 27% were from labor work. 82% of them were preferring bidi over cigarette. Among them 66% have started smoking in early childhood between 10-20 years of age. 57% have family history of smoking and 24% were influenced by peers for smoking initiation. 79% have tried to leave the smoking. 69% were knowing ban of smoking at public places and 72% were knowing warning signs over bidi/ cigarette packs. 90% were knowing about adverse health effects of smoking.

Conclusion and recommendations: Although people are well aware of effect of smoking, they still continue to smoke. A strict implementation of the law and its regular monitoring should be done in public places to prevent public from smoking.

Keywords: Adverse health effect, Awareness, Smoking.

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Introduction

Smoking damages almost all of the body's organs and creating long term debility among smokers. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), emphysema, chronic bronchitis like lung diseases diabetes, cancer, heart disease and stroke like disorders are contributed by smoking. In addition, smoking raises the risk of developing tuberculosis, several eye conditions, and immune system issues including rheumatoid arthritis.[1]

According to the Global Adult Tobacco Survey India, 2016–17, about 267 million adults in India (15 years of age and older) use tobacco, making up 29% of all adults in the country. In addition to causing fatalities, smoking has significant negative social and financial effects.[2] In India, total economic expenditures of all diseases related to tobacco use for those 35 years of age and over in 2017–18 was INR 177 341 crore. In India, tobacco use is the fourth-highest risk factor for death and disability

when combined in 2019. It is estimated that tobacco use results in about 1.2 million fatalities. One million people die from smoking, 240 thousand from second-hand smoke, and 35,000 from chewing tobacco.

In India, ischemic heart disease (IHD), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and stroke are the leading causes of mortality. Tobacco use contributed to 354.7 thousand IHD deaths, or 20% of all deaths, 424.7 thousand COPD deaths, and 98.5 thousand stroke fatalities, or 14% of all deaths in 2019..[3] Various studies have been conducted in India regarding awareness and practices regarding smoking and its harmful effect knowledge, but very few studies have been done within hospital beneficiaries and their relative regarding smoking awareness. This study is a small effort to study the awareness of smoking among them.

Methodology

This study was done with the purpose of assessing the knowledge and practice regarding smoking and its adverse health effects among people who were caught smoking in a tertiary care hospital, Gujarat. A cross sectional study was conducted by students as a part of PSBH (Problem solving for better health) project. The students were posted for two months in community medicine department for research process experiences. Under this process students were trained for three days regarding PSBH project and research details. Students were guided to identify problems existing in particular geography and finding out solutions for the same. Students were assigned one guide for the processing and completing project. After four hours of brainstorming session with guide students identified the smoker's entry and smoking in hospital premises is a problem. They have prepared following study details after one day of discussion.

Any area falling in premises of hospital, including, all OPD area, waiting area, wards, walking lobbies, nearby places, roads passing through hospital, kitchen areas, disposal areas, trauma area were screened for people smoking while our visit from duration of Aug 15- November 15, 2021. All the visitors of tertiary care hospital at given time duration and who have been found smoking any premises area were included in this study. This includes patients, their relatives, even workers in the hospital who have been smoking any area. People were asked for consent and were interviewed. A total of 100 participants were interviewed in this duration with preformed pretested Performa. Non willing person, seriously injured person, mentally ill, not well oriented people were excluded from study.

After completion of data collection, visitors were counselled and advised regarding smoking and second hand smoking health effects. They were also advised to quit the smoking.

Data were entered and analysed using Microsoft excel. Numbers, Percentages and proportion were used to analyse the data. Codes and check were used to maintain the quality of data.

Results:

Majority of the population found smoking were male (91%), only 09 % were female. As compare to males, females were less among smokers but their sharing percentage getting increasing day by day. Among smokers 54% population were 36-50 years of age. Majority of them belongs to laborer working background (27%). 73% were married and 30% were studied up to secondary level. People having good study background were also found smoking in hospital premises e.g. 12% were graduate and 7% were post graduate study level and they were well aware people. Majority of them earned 5000-10000 (43%) monthly, people having good income were also found smoking in premises. (Table-1)

Among smokers' majority caught were smoking bidi, those were 82%. They also have preference of bidi as smoking choice. They have started smoking as early in 10-20 years of age (66%). Friends have had influenced majority to start and continue the smoking in 24%. Even 57% participants had family history of near one smoking. 58% were spending 400-600 rs per month for smoking purchases. Among them 79% have tried to leave the smoking for one or another reason and 32% have started to reduce the doses for leaving smoking. 29% have taken help of faith healers also to leave the smoking. (Table-2)

On asking awareness regarding smoking ban in public place 69% knew the law but were not following the same. 72% were aware about having warning sign over the bidi/ cigarette packets. Among them, 90% were knowing about adverse health effect on their selves and 69% knew smoking affects others health also. 77% knew that smoking affects lungs, 41% knew effect on heart, 23% effect on brain and 22% knew that it affects the routine gut digestions and effect on GIT. (Table-3) Based on above table, 21% individuals from study group were having issues related to breathing and 32% have some level of cough. 24% person were found to have some of the digestion issues. 17% participants have been found to have diabetes or hypertension or other NCDs. (Table-4)

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of participants

Age Group (years)	Number (%)
< 19 years	08(8%)
21-35	20(20%)
36-50	54(54%)
51-60	11(11%)
>60	07(7%)
Gender	
Male	91(91%)
Female	09(09%)
Occupation	

Government job	19(19%)
Private job	16(16%)
Laborer	27(27%)
Farmer	23(23%)
Diamond worker	08(8%)
Not working	07(7%)
Marital status	
married	73(73%)
Unmarried/single	19(19%)
Divorcee/separated	08(8%)
Education	
illiterate	11(11%)
Up to primary	27(27%)
Up to secondary	30(30%)
Up to higher secondary	13(13%)
Graduate	12(12%)
Post graduate	07(7%)
Average income per month	
<5000	12(12%)
5000-10,000	43(43%)
10,000-20,000	31(31%)
>20,0000	14(14%)

Table 2: Knowledge and practices related to smoking among participants

Characteristic	Number (%)
Form of smoking	
Cigarette	15 (15%)
Bidi	82(82%)
Didn't replied	03(3%)
Age of started smoking	
10-20	66(66%)
21-30	22(22%)
31-40	10(10%)
41-50	2(2%)
Reasons to start	
To enjoy	18(18%)
To feel relieved	21(21%)
Due to friends	24(24%)
Started without reason	12(12%)
Not possible to leave now	14(14%)
For social benefit	11(11%)
Family history of smoking	
Yes	57(57%)
no	43(43%)
Monthly expenditure on smoking	
<200	05(5%)
200-400	34(34%)
400-600	58(58%)
>600	03(3%)

Table 3: Leaving efforts and warning awareness among participants

Characteristic	Number (%)
Ever tried to leave smoking	
Yes	79(79%)
no	21(21%)
Efforts made to leave smoking	
Go to doctor	13(13%)
Go to counsellor	09(9%)

Reduce the doses	32(32%)
Got drug prescription	17(17%)
Go to faith healers	29(29%)
Awareness about secondhand smoking and its effect on others	
Yes	69(69%)
No	31(31%)
Harmful impact awareness	
Impact on lung	77(77%)
Impact on heart	41(41%)
Impact on brain	23(23%)
Impact on GIT	22(22%)
Awareness regarding prohibition in public place	
Yes	69(69%)
No	31(31%)
Awareness regarding signs on packaging	
Warning sign on packet	72(72%)
Effect on one's own body	90(90%)
Effect on others' body	69(69%)

Table 4: Self-reported health effects currently faced by participants

Health problems of smoking	Number (%)
Difficulty in breathing	21(21%)
Cough	32 (32%)
Hypertension /Diabetes or other NCDs	17 (17%)
Headache	06 (06%)
Digestion related issues	24 (24%)
Poor vision	08 (8%)
Memory issue	04 (4%)

Discussion:

In our study we found that 66% participants had onset of smoking from 10-20 years of age. In a study done in school children in Noida, found mean age of starting smoking was 12.5 years.[4] Various reasons has been found for such tender age initiation of smoking as given in the table 1.

In our study reason for getting addicted is due to friend's circle. A study done in 300 participants, with 80.3% most participants (87.7%) said that they become accustomed to smoking due to peer pressure, with the belief that smoking is a sign of maturity.[5] Although to feel relieved from stress (24%) and to feel good (18%) are the reasons to have this addiction, majority are getting this as social habit as part of their peer group or social group like from family environment.

In this study 79% have tried to leave the smoking for one or another reason. Even 32% have started to reduce the doses for leaving smoking and 29% have gone of faith healers also to leave the smoking. Although stopping smoking is a personal decision, in terms of their behavior, study done in Karnataka state has found 89.4% participants have made prior attempts to stop smoking, and 78.8% have gotten medical counsel to stop smoking.[6] Taking help from various therapy may help to quit in smoking.[7] A study has observed that higher

percentage of younger adults aged 18–24 years were interested in quitting the habit (100%) compared to those aged 45–64 years (85.2%). [8]

On asking awareness regarding smoking ban in public place 69% knows the law but not following the same.72% were aware about having warning sign over the bidi/ cigarate packets. Among them, 90% were knowing about adverse health effect on their selves and 69% knew smoking affects others health also.77% knew that smoking affects lungs, 41% knew effect on heart, 23% effect on brain and 22% knew that it affects the routing gut digestions and effect on GIT. In a study done in Karnataka, study included 160 male patients in total. The majority of individuals were well-informed on the negative effects of tobacco use. Roughly 96% of respondents were aware that smoking increased their risk of developing certain cancers, and 93.8% understood that smoking was a major contributor to a number of serious illnesses. The majority of patients (98.1%) believed that stopping smoking was a personal decision, and 96.3% agreed that it is illegal to smoke in public areas.[6] Less awareness having ban of smoking and various health effect of smoking has been found the reason for continuing smoking willingly in public places.

Recommendations

1. A strict implementation of smoking ban should be done in public health facilities like hospitals, parks, schools, markets etc. People even aware about, take opportunity in unmonitored places for smoking and influences others health also. Contiguous monitoring of such public places and fine ailment should be done to set an example.
2. Early age of onset of starting very first smoking and family, peer influence has been observed in our study. School programs should be implemented to make children awareness regarding firsthand smoking and second hand smoking and its long term impacts. Children are need to frequently sensitize about the issues through street plays, mimes, dramas and education.
3. People have been found knowing about health hazards of smoking and have also tried to leave this addiction. But because of stigma felt by people they go to faith healers and others. A wide awareness campaign all over the country should run and easy availability of de-addiction centers and experts should be done. Empathetic approach and throughout help will help them to quit tobacco.

Limitation of study

Our study has been conducted in very short duration planning so there was limited sample size. Heterogeneous population limit the generalization of results.

Future scope

Present study suggests there is need of creating more awareness related to smoking and its health hazards through banners, media, advertisements and strict implementation of the law of ban of smoking in hospitals.

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